

PODCASTING: A LOCALIZED SUPPLEMENTARY LEARNING TOOL IN ENHANCING AGRICULTURAL LITERACY

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Podcasting: A Localized Supplementary Learning Tool in Enhancing Agricultural Literacy

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Abstract

This study determined the effectiveness of integrating podcasts into learners' lessons to enhance agricultural literacy. Through quantitative methods, including surveys and pre-and post-tests, the study assessed the effectiveness of podcast integration in improving learners' cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains of agri-crop production. The researcher selected two sections of grade 7 from a junior high school in the division of Tanuan City. The researcher used an experimental method to determine the effectiveness of podcast integration. The study revealed that the respondents perceived the integration of podcasting as a localized learning tool in terms of localized lessons, localized discussions, and localized interviews as highly appreciated because of the relatability and practicality of the lesson. On account of the student's perceptions regarding the utilization of podcast design in terms of length, pedagogical approach, style, and fit with other materials, they strongly agree on all the indicators that were interpreted as highly favorable. Moreover, the study reveals a statistically significant difference in the level of agricultural literacy among students before and after the utilization of podcasting as a localized learning tool in agri-crop production across the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor competency domains. The use of the localized podcast content significantly increased their scores based on the administered assessment.

Keywords: *podcast, lesson, discussion, interview, length, style, fit with other materials*

Introduction

Agriculture plays a significant role in the Philippine economy. Involving about 40 percent of Filipino workers contributes an average of 20 percent to the Gross Domestic Product. Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) is a skill-based subject offered in Grade 7, which includes an Agriculture component to encourage learners to become interested in Agriculture over other popular courses for food production and security in the future. Furthermore, the learning journey outside the four corners of the classrooms for every Tanaueño goes beyond the printed materials. As they stay at home, DepEd Memorandum No. 053, s. 2020 encourages the establishment of Gulayan sa Tahanan, or Urban Vegetable Gardening at Home for personal consumption and to improve their family members' income, health, and well-being. The teacher always gives extra effort and assistance to the learners to make this project possible. One of their ways is to give different instructional tools and materials to help the learners achieve the required competencies to be learned. Since Tanaueño learners have their tablets, they are now more open to new technologies as an educational tool, and podcasting is no different.

Many learning institutions are cutting back on textbooks and investing in technology-enhanced learning. A "podcast" is a digital audio file available for download on a computer or a mobile device. It is a portmanteau of "iPod" and "broadcast." Podcasts can be used as a replacement for traditional lectures or as a supplement to concepts taught during face-to-face lectures, and they can be utilized to aid learning from both an aural and visual perspective. (Kratochwill et al., 2016) Teachers can leverage podcasts as a learning tool. Traditional teaching methods rely heavily on the lecture format, the standard in many classrooms. The agriculturist is now using podcast as they produce portable news for farmers and ranchers because of the absence of agriculture news in some rural radio markets; podcasting can fill that void with a variety of news and educational programming, targeting both agricultural producers and public for the agricultural awareness and literacy.

Agricultural literacy was initially defined as understanding food and fiber systems within historical and socio-economic contexts (National et al., 1988). Over time, agricultural literacy has expanded from knowledge attainment to incorporate critical thinking skills and affective constructs such as attitudes (Vallera & Bodzin, 2016), engagement in agricultural systems, and behaviors (Spielmaker et al., 2014). Hence, agriculturally literate citizens are informed decision-makers able to participate in civic, cultural, and economic affairs related to agriculture. Because of this emphasis on civic engagement and decision-making, the most recent agricultural literacy frameworks identify knowledge, awareness, attitudes, skills, and behavior as key components (Roberts et al., 2016).

The news in agriculture and food in 2021 was dominated by deteriorating food security. Approximately 30 percent of the world's population lacked adequate food in 2020 and 2021. COVID-19 also pushed more people into poverty and made the poor poorer worldwide. Today, supplies of many commodities remain at their tightest levels in years, which will likely prolong inflationary pressure for food well into the new year. As a result, 2022 will be another year of unprecedented supply and demand shocks, tight food supplies, and uncertain climate conditions. Of the 291 million additional people suffering from food insecurity globally, 72% are in Asia. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority, in the fourth quarter of 2021, the value of production in agriculture and fisheries at constant 2018 prices increased by 0.6 percent. This was attributed to the production increments in crops, poultry, and fisheries. Crop production grew by 2.6 percent. It shared 59.1 percent of the total agriculture and fisheries production. Palay and corn posted expansions in production at 0.2 percent and 28.6 percent, respectively. At current prices, the production value in agriculture and fisheries amounted

to Php 560.39 billion in the fourth quarter of 2021. This was 0.6 percent higher than the previous year's level. But this was not enough to offset the dismal figures recorded in the previous quarters. The first quarter registered -3.3%, while the second and third quarters posted -1.5% and -2.6%, respectively.

Tanauan City is a second-class city with a land area of 10 967.43 hectares, about 3.47% of the province's total land area. Industrialization and the city's increasing population had decreased the land area allotted to agriculture. Based on the Farmers Registry System, the city has 2 866 farmers, or 1.88% of its population. Almost 70% of the total agricultural land area of Tanauan City is covered with sugarcane plants, which were included in the damages caused by typhoon Odette. Since agriculture is one of the courses offered in technology and livelihood education, DepEd Tanauan City prioritizes offering this course to every Grade 7 learner. The TLE Education Program Supervisor supported the project under DepEd Memorandum No. 053, s. 2020 encourages the establishment of Gulayan sa Tahanan, or Urban Vegetable Gardening at Home, for personal consumption and to improve their family members' income, health, and well-being. The teachers made localized teaching and learning materials to improve the agricultural engagement of the learners. However, the agricultural literacy of the learners in Malaking Pulo is still low, as reflected in their scores for written works and performance tasks. The average grade of 94 students was 79.69% for the first quarter of SY 2022-2023.

The researcher has found Podcasting to be a tool for educational purposes. This can be used as content in teacher-made localized materials. Podcasting fits the current education set-up in Malaking Pulo National High School, where the implemented modality is Modular Distance Learning. The researcher will use a Podcast as the learning tool through teachers' created Podcast educational content about Agriculture through discussions, interviews, and narratives featuring local farmers from their community.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of localized podcast content as a learning tool in enhancing the agricultural literacy of the students. Specifically, this sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents as to:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. family income?
2. What is the students' perception on podcasting as supplementary learning tool terms of:
 - 2.1. localized lesson;
 - 2.2. localized discussion; and
 - 2.3. localized interview?
3. How do the students perceive the utilization of podcast design in terms of:
 - 3.1. length;
 - 3.2. pedagogical approach;
 - 3.3. style; and
 - 3.4. fit with other materials?
4. What is the level of agricultural literacy of the students before and after the utilization of podcasting as a localized learning tool in agri-crop production in terms of the following domains:
 - 4.1. cognitive;
 - 4.2. affective; and
 - 4.3. psychomotor?
5. Is there a significant difference between the agricultural literacy of Grade 7 learners before and after the utilization of podcasting in agri-crop production?

Methodology

Research Design

The design of this study is experimental research. The research is experimental. When a systematic and scientific approach is employed, and one or more variables is/are manipulated, then any change in the other variables is controlled and measured (Mitchell, 2015). This research is experimental because it determined the effect of podcasting in the students' agricultural literacy.

Respondents

Seventy-two (72 Grade 7 TLE) learners took up TLE Exploratory Courses at Malaking Pulo National High School. Regardless of their average rating in TLE, all students were the study's respondents. They were assumed to have multi- learning practices in understanding TLE concepts and academic performance based on their curriculum grade level.

Instruments

The researcher's primary instrument for gathering data was the survey questionnaire, which consisted of two parts. The first part focused on the learners' perceptions of the integration of podcasting as a localized supplementary learning tool, and the second part focused on

how students performed after utilizing podcast design.

However, the instrument questionnaire about agricultural literacy was used to determine the students' mean scores in cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains. +

To establish the instrument's validity and reliability, the TLE teachers examined and refined the questionnaire during the thesis proposal. All suggestions and advice from the panelists were incorporated into the questionnaire.

In gathering data relevant to this study, the researcher used the following: (1) Localized Podcast Content, (2) Pretest/Post; and (3) Teacher-Made Survey Questionnaire;

Teacher-Made Podcast Content: The Teacher-Made Podcast Content is a supplementary learning tool designed to enrich traditional classroom lessons. Each episode features localized lessons, discussions, and interviews tailored to the local agricultural context, providing students with relevant insights and connections to their surroundings. The content is carefully aligned with specific learning competencies outlined in the curriculum, ensuring that students enjoy the episodes and acquire valuable knowledge and skills. The teacher considers various design elements such as episode length, pedagogical approaches, and style to optimize engagement and educational impact. Moreover, the podcasts seamlessly integrate with other instructional materials, enhancing the learning experience. Specifically tailored for lessons about agri crop production, these podcasts offer additional insights, real-world examples, and expert perspectives, deepening students' understanding and fostering a greater appreciation for the subject matter. Overall, the Teacher-Made Podcast Content represents an innovative approach to agricultural education, leveraging audio storytelling to enhance student learning and engagement in the study of crop production.

Pretest/Posttest: The pretest was administered before the lesson began, as a baseline assessment of the participant's existing knowledge and understanding of the subject matter. Following the lesson on competencies such as "Tools and Equipment in Farming," "Preventive Maintenance of the Tools and Equipment," and "Interpret Plans and Drawings," learners engaged with podcasting as a localized supplementary learning tool. This tool was designed to reinforce key concepts discussed during the lesson and facilitate deeper comprehension. After learners had utilized the supplementary learning tool and engaged with podcast content created by the teacher, a posttest was administered. By comparing the results of the pretest and posttest, researchers could determine the effectiveness of the educational intervention in enhancing the participants' knowledge and skills in the targeted competencies. In developing the pretest/posttest, the researcher adhered to standard procedures in developing and validating a test, beginning with developing test specifications and gathering evidence that supported the validity and estimated the reliability of the test.

Teacher-Made Survey Questionnaire: This questionnaire was administered to identify students' perceptions of integrating podcast content as a supplementary learning tool and their perceived effectiveness of podcast design and content. This served as the basis for designing the podcast content.

Procedure

The research procedure involved utilizing a podcast as a targeted supplementary learning tool aimed at enhancing agricultural literacy among learners. The podcast content, created by the teacher, was carefully developed with considerations for its length, pedagogical approach, style, and alignment with existing course materials. The procedure began with learners engaging in discussions related to the topic of study. Following these discussions, the podcast was introduced as a supplemental resource to further enhance their understanding. Learners then actively utilized the podcast to reinforce and deepen their grasp of the subject matter. A structured research design was implemented to assess the effectiveness of this approach. Prior to engaging with the podcast, learners completed a pretest to establish baseline knowledge. After the initial discussions and podcast utilization, a post-test was administered to evaluate the impact of the podcast on learning outcomes. This comparative assessment allowed researchers to measure the podcast's effectiveness in improving agricultural literacy among students within the study.

To carry out the study until its completion, a letter of request for approval was handed over personally by the researcher to the school principal. The researcher asked permission from the department head to conduct a study on the Junior High School students, particularly the Grade 7 learners of Malaking Pulo High School. After obtaining approval, survey questionnaires were utilized to gather information from the students and TLE teachers. The questionnaires were retrieved, carefully tallied, and encoded by the researcher.

Data Analysis

To answer the problems raised in the study, the following statistical tools were employed:

Mean and standard deviation. These were used to determine the students' performance level before and after utilizing localized podcast content.

Paired T-test. This was used to test for the significant difference between the pretest and posttest results and the learners' agricultural literacy before and after utilizing localized podcast content.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the details regarding the results of the study. The discussions and corresponding interpretations of the statistical results follow the order of the problem and the hypothesis that guides this investigation.

Table 1. Students' Profile as to Sex, Age and Income

<i>Sex (n = 72)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Male	45	62.5
Female	27	37.5
<i>Age (n = 72)</i>		
13 and below	69	95.8
14	3	4.2
<i>Income (n = 72)</i>		
1- 10,000 – 15,000	50	69.4
2- 16,000 – 20,000	13	18.1
3- 21,000 – 25,000	5	6.9
5- 26,000 and above	4	5.6

Table 1 shows the age profile of the respondents. It shows that most are male (45) 62.5% while only (27) 37.5% female. In terms of age, the majority are 13 and below at (69) 95.8%, while only (3) 4.2% are 14. Moreover, in terms of the family's income, the majority belongs to 10,000 – 15,000 at (50) 69.4%, followed by 16,000 – 20,000 at (13) 18.1%, then 21,000 – 25,000 at (5) 6.9% and there are only few who have their income of 26,000 and above at (4) 5.6%. These indicate a predominance of male participants, comprising 62.5% of the sample, compared to 37.5% female. This sex skew might suggest a higher interest or accessibility among males toward the subject matter or the podcasting platform. Secondly, the overwhelming majority of respondents, 95.8%, fall within the age bracket of 13 and below, indicating a strong presence of younger individuals in the study. This finding implies a potential focus on educational initiatives targeting children and adolescents, aligning with the study's objective of enhancing agricultural literacy. Lastly, the distribution of family income levels showcases a concentration in the lower to middle-income brackets, with 69.4% falling within the 10,000 – 15,000 range. This socio-economic pattern suggests a potential disparity in access to resources or technology for higher-income families, which could influence the effectiveness and reach of podcast-based educational interventions in agricultural literacy.

Table 2. Students' Perception on Podcasting as Supplementary Learning Tool for Localized Lesson

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. Local farmers participating in the lessons ignite our eagerness to learn more about different farm tools and equipment.	4.40	0.61	Agree
2. Having local experts provides important insights and hands-on farming knowledge.	4.56	0.62	Strongly agree
3. The podcast lesson focuses on our local situation, matching what we're interested in.	4.32	0.71	Agree
4. The local podcast lesson covers all the important farming tools and equipment thoroughly.	4.74	0.47	Strongly agree
5. The local lesson uses real examples from nearby farms to show concepts, making it relatable to us.	4.74	0.55	Strongly agree
Mean	4.55	0.32	Strongly agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 (Strongly Agree) 3.50-4.49 (Agree) 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Agree) 1.50-2.49 (Disagree) 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 2 presents students' perceptions regarding integrating podcasting as a localized learning tool in terms of localized lessons. In terms of localized lessons, the overall mean is 4.55, which is interpreted as strongly agreeing. The highest mean is 4.74, stating that the local podcast lesson covers all the important farming tools and equipment thoroughly, and the local lesson uses real examples from nearby farms to show concepts, making it relevant to the learners. This indicates that the lesson effectively provides comprehensive information on essential tools and equipment, likely enhancing participants' understanding and skills in farming practices. Similarly, the mean score of 4.74 for using real examples from nearby farms to illustrate concepts indicates that participants highly appreciate the relatability and practicality of the lesson. By incorporating local examples, the lesson becomes more engaging and applicable to participants' experiences, improving learning retention and motivation.

However, the lowest mean is 4.32, stating that the podcast lesson focuses on our local situation and matches respondents' interest. This could mean that there may be room for improvement in tailoring the content even more closely to their specific needs and challenges. This finding highlights the importance of ongoing feedback and customization in educational content delivery to ensure maximum relevance and effectiveness.

Table 3. *Students' Perception on Podcasting as Supplementary Learning Tool for Localized Discussion*

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. The discussion encourages active exchanges between farmers and teachers, keeping us engaged.	4.68	0.57	Strongly agree
2. The podcast talks about using the ideas in our local area, showing how to use the knowledge in our daily lives or work.	4.57	0.59	Strongly agree
3. The podcast talks about solving local farming problems, and suggests solutions to overcome these challenges.	4.44	0.68	Agree
4. The discussions are organized, easy to understand, and clear.	4.38	0.69	Agree
5. The local farmers joining the discussion offer different views and ideas about the topic.	4.63	0.56	Strongly agree
Mean	4.54	0.35	Strongly agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 (Strongly Agree) 3.50-4.49 (Agree) 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Agree) 1.50-2.49 (Disagree) 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 3 presents students' perception regarding the integration of podcasting as a localized learning tool in terms of localized discussions. The overall mean is 4.54 interpreted as strongly agree. The highest mean is 4.68 stating that the discussion encourages active exchanges between farmers and teachers, keeping them engaged while lowest is 4.38 which stated that the discussions are organized, easy to understand, and clear.

The high mean score of 4.68 for the discussion encouraging active exchanges between farmers and teachers indicates that students strongly agree that podcasting integration fosters dynamic interactions and engagement during discussions. This suggests that the format effectively facilitates dialogue and collaboration, allowing for the exchange of ideas, experiences, and insights between participants and educators. Active exchanges can promote deeper understanding and critical thinking, as well as create a sense of community and shared learning among participants. Conversely, the lower mean score of 4.38 for the discussions being organized, easy to understand, and clear suggests that while participants generally agree that the discussions are effective, there may be some room for improvement in terms of clarity and organization. This finding implies that there might be instances where discussions could be better structured or communicated to enhance comprehension and coherence.

Clear and well-organized discussions are essential for ensuring that participants can fully grasp the content and engage meaningfully with the material. These findings highlight the strengths of integrating podcasting as a localized learning tool, particularly in fostering active exchanges and engagement during discussions. Then, it must be put into consideration implementing strategies to enhance the organization and clarity of discussions, such as providing clear guidelines or summaries, structuring discussions around specific topics or objectives, and facilitating opportunities for clarification or elaboration as needed.

Additionally, ongoing feedback and reflection on the effectiveness of discussions can inform iterative improvements to the podcasting integration, ensuring that it continues to meet the needs and preferences of participants.

Table 4. *Students' Perception on Podcasting as Supplementary Learning Tool for Localized Interview*

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. The interview included skilled farmers and a 'Gulayan sa Paaralan' coordinator who are experienced in understanding farming plans.	4.85	0.36	Strongly agree
2. The interviewer asked interesting questions that made the guest share valuable thoughts and experiences.	4.56	0.59	Strongly agree
3. The questions in the interview make the guest share real stories from the community that help us understand important ideas.	4.63	0.59	Agree
4. The recording is clear and helps us understand the guest's conversation with the interviewer.	4.35	0.78	Agree
5. Both the guest and the interviewer used respectful and inclusive language, making the atmosphere welcoming.	4.89	0.31	Strongly agree
Mean	4.65	0.28	Strongly agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 (Strongly Agree) 3.50-4.49 (Agree) 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Agree) 1.50-2.49 (Disagree) 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 4 presents students' perception regarding the integration of podcasting as a localized learning tool in terms of localized interviews. The overall mean is 4.65 interpreted as strongly agree. The highest mean is 4.89 stating both the guest and the interviewer used respectful and inclusive language, making the atmosphere welcoming while lowest is 4.35 which stated that the recording is clear and helps us understand the guest's conversation with the interviewer. The overall mean score suggests a strong agreement among the participants. The highest mean score indicates that both the guest and the interviewer utilized respectful and inclusive language, thereby fostering a welcoming atmosphere. Conversely, the lowest mean score suggests that there may be room for improvement in terms of the clarity of the recordings and their effectiveness in aiding comprehension of the conversation between the guest and the interviewer.

The high overall mean score of 4.65 indicates a strong agreement among participants regarding the integration of podcasting as a localized learning tool, reflecting positive perceptions of its effectiveness. Specifically, the highest mean score of 4.89 for both the

guest and the interviewer using respectful and inclusive language highlights the importance of creating a welcoming and inclusive atmosphere within the podcast format. This finding suggests that participants appreciate and value the respectful communication and inclusive language used during interviews, which can contribute to a positive learning environment and foster a sense of belonging among listeners.

On the other hand, the lowest mean score of 4.35 for the clarity of the recordings and their effectiveness in aiding comprehension of the conversation between the guest and the interviewer suggests that there may be room for improvement in this aspect of the podcasting integration. Clear and comprehensible recordings are essential for ensuring that participants can fully understand and engage with the content presented in the interviews. This finding indicates a potential need for enhancements in recording quality, editing, or presentation techniques to improve the overall clarity and effectiveness of the interviews. The findings reveal the importance of considering both content and technical aspects when integrating podcasting as a localized learning tool. While positive feedback regarding the respectful and inclusive language used in interviews is encouraging, addressing areas for improvement in recording clarity and comprehension can further enhance the overall effectiveness of the podcasting format.

Table 5. *Summary Table of Students' Perception on Podcasting as Supplementary Learning Tool for Localization*

Variables	Mean	SD	VI
Localized lesson	4.55	0.32	Strongly agree
Localized discussion	4.54	0.35	Strongly agree
Localized interview	4.65	0.28	Strongly agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 (Strongly Agree) 3.50-4.49 (Agree) 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Agree) 1.50-2.49 (Disagree) 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 5 presents students on perception on podcasting as supplementary learning tool for localization across three sub-variables: localized lessons, discussions, and interviews.

Among the sub-variables, the highest mean score is observed in the localized interview segment, with a mean score of 4.65, indicating a strong agreement among students. Particularly, students highly appreciate the inclusion of skilled farmers and a coordinator experienced in farming plans, the interviewer's ability to pose engaging questions, the relevance of questions prompting real community stories, the clarity of the recording facilitating understanding, and the respectful and inclusive language used by both the guest and interviewer, fostering a welcoming atmosphere. On the other hand, the lowest mean score is found in the localized lesson segment, with a mean score of 4.55, still indicating a strong agreement but slightly lower than the other segments. Students value the involvement of local farmers and experts igniting their eagerness to learn, the focus on local situations matching their interests, the thorough coverage of farming tools and equipment, the use of real examples from nearby farms to illustrate concepts, and the active exchanges between farmers and teachers during discussions.

Implications from these results suggest that students highly value the incorporation of localized elements in podcasting for educational purposes. The prominence of skilled local experts, real-life examples, and community-relevant content resonates strongly with students, enhancing their engagement and comprehension.

The positive result from the creation of localized lessons, discussions, and interviews through podcasts aligns with the integrated use of podcasts as described by Abdous et al. (2012). By developing podcasts that feature localized content, such as lessons tailored to specific contexts, engaging discussions relevant to students' experiences, and interviews with local practitioners or experts, educators can enrich the learning experience beyond traditional classroom methods. This approach resonates with the integrated use of podcasts as described in the literature, where podcasts serve not only to supplement existing coursework but also to introduce new and unique content that fosters deeper engagement and critical thinking. Localized podcasts offer an opportunity to bridge theory with practical application, providing students with real-world insights and perspectives that enhance their understanding of course material and promote a more interactive and personalized learning environment. Therefore, the positive impact of these localized podcasts underscores the value of integrating podcasts into educational practice to facilitate meaningful learning experiences tailored to the specific needs and interests of students.

Table 6 showcases students' perception regarding the utilization of podcast design in terms of length. The overall mean score for students' perception of podcast design utilization is 4.36, indicating a strong agreement across all evaluated aspects. Among the statements, the highest mean score is attributed to the clarity and conciseness of the podcast, with a mean score of 4.49. This suggests that students highly value podcasts that are clear and to the point, avoiding lengthy discussions that could potentially lead to a loss of interest. This emphasizes the importance of maintaining a succinct and focused approach in podcast content creation to effectively engage learners. Conversely, the lowest mean score pertains to the consistency in episode length, with a mean score of 4.26. While still indicating a strong agreement, this suggests a slightly lower level of satisfaction compared to other aspects. Ensuring consistent episode lengths can contribute to a sense of predictability and comfort among students, allowing them to know what to expect from each podcast episode. These findings suggest that students appreciate podcast designs that prioritize clarity, conciseness, and engaging beginnings.

Table 6. *Students' Perception on the Utilization of Podcast Design as to Length*

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. The podcast was brief, around 5 to 15 minutes, so we stayed engaged and focused.	4.35	0.71	Agree
2. The start of the local podcast is interesting and grabs our attention, making the learning efficient.	4.31	0.61	Agree
3. The podcast was clear and to the point, avoiding long talks that could make us lose interest.	4.49	0.55	Agree
4. The episodes are consistently the same length, making us comfortable and knowing what to expect.	4.26	0.62	Agree
5. The podcast caters to our preference for shorter, more frequent episodes that suit our learning style.	4.42	0.74	Agree
Mean	4.36	0.41	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 (Strongly Agree) 3.50-4.49 (Agree) 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Agree) 1.50-2.49 (Disagree) 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 7 showcases students' perception regarding the utilization of podcast design in terms of pedagogical approach. The overall mean score for students' perception of this pedagogical approach is 4.44, indicating a strong agreement across all evaluated aspects. The highest mean score is associated with the statement "Working together on podcast lessons helped me understand the topic better," with a mean score of 4.63. This suggests that students highly value collaborative learning experiences facilitated through podcasting, emphasizing the effectiveness of group engagement in enhancing comprehension and knowledge retention. Conversely, the lowest mean score pertains to the statement "My critical thinking skill has improved because of listening to podcast discussions," with a mean score of 4.24. Although still indicating a strong agreement, this suggests a slightly lower level of perceived improvement in critical thinking skills compared to other aspects. This may indicate a potential area for further emphasis on promoting critical thinking through podcast-based discussions. These findings highlight the effectiveness of collaborative learning approaches in podcasting, as evidenced by the high mean score associated with working together on podcast lessons. Educators can leverage this insight to encourage more collaborative and interactive podcasting experiences to enhance student engagement and understanding.

Table 7. *Students' Perception on the Utilization of Podcast Design as to Pedagogical Approach*

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. I feel positive about learning through lecture-style podcasts.	4.53	0.62	Strongly agree
2. I stay focused and engaged during podcast lectures.	4.29	0.7	Agree
3. My critical thinking skill has improved because of listening to podcast discussion.	4.24	0.61	Agree
4. I will apply insights gained from podcast discussions to real-world situations.	4.5	0.7	Strongly agree
5. Working together on podcast lessons helped me understand the topic better.	4.63	0.51	Strongly agree
Mean	4.44	0.42	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 (Strongly Agree) 3.50-4.49 (Agree) 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Agree) 1.50-2.49 (Disagree) 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 8 showcases students' perception regarding the utilization of podcast design as to style. In evaluating the style of the podcast, students express a strong agreement across all aspects, with an overall mean score of 4.56. This indicates a high level of satisfaction with the podcast's informal and engaging tone. The highest mean score is associated with the statement "The host and guests keep a good pace in the podcast, using pauses well to help us understand," with a mean score of 4.64.

Table 8. *Students' Perception on the Utilization of Podcast Design as to Style*

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. The podcast is informal and fun, with the guest and host using humor to keep us interested.	4.54	0.55	Strongly agree
2. The podcast had a casual and funny tone, making the episode lively.	4.6	0.54	Strongly agree
3. The host and guests talk clearly, so we easily understand everything.	4.56	0.62	Strongly agree
4. The host and guests keep a good pace in the podcast, using pauses well to help us understand.	4.64	0.58	Strongly agree
5. The podcast has a steady style across episodes, giving us a familiar and recognizable experience.	4.46	0.66	Agree
Mean	4.56	0.36	Strongly agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 (Strongly Agree) 3.50-4.49 (Agree) 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Agree) 1.50-2.49 (Disagree) 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

This suggests that students highly appreciate the pacing and clarity of communication within the podcast, indicating its effectiveness in facilitating comprehension and engagement. Conversely, the lowest mean score is attributed to the statement "The podcast has a steady style across episodes, giving us a familiar and recognizable experience," with a mean score of 4.46. While still indicating strong agreement, this suggests a slightly lower level of consistency compared to other aspects. Maintaining a consistent style across episodes can enhance the overall listening experience, providing students with a predictable and familiar format that promotes continuity and coherence. These findings emphasize the importance of pacing, clarity, and consistency in podcast style. Educators and podcast creators can leverage these insights to optimize the design and delivery of podcast content, ensuring that it remains engaging, understandable,

and cohesive across episodes.

Table 9. *Students' Perception on the Utilization of Podcast Design as to Fit with Other Materials*

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. The podcast matches our subject's learning goals, improving our overall learning experience.	4.86	0.35	Strongly agree
2. The teacher provides extra materials like modules and guides to go with the podcast.	4.54	0.57	Strongly agree
3. The podcast followed the module's structure, making it easy to navigate and find information for reviewing.	4.54	0.6	Strongly agree
4. The podcast works well with other resources like books, videos, and modules to strengthen learning.	4.68	0.55	Strongly agree
5. The content uses the same terms and ideas throughout the podcast and other materials, avoid confusion and improved understanding.	4.57	0.52	Strongly agree
Mean	4.64	0.32	Strongly agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 (Strongly Agree) 3.50-4.49 (Agree) 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Agree) 1.50-2.49 (Disagree) 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 9 showcases students' perception regarding the utilization of podcast design as to fit with other materials. The analysis of the fit of the podcast with other materials indicates a strong agreement among students, with an impressive overall mean score of 4.64. This suggests that students highly value the integration of podcasts with other learning resources to enhance their overall learning experience. The highest mean score is associated with the statement "The podcast matches our subject's learning goals, improving our overall learning experience," with an exceptionally high mean score of 4.86. This underscores the significant alignment between the podcast content and the learning objectives, indicating that students perceive the podcast as highly beneficial for achieving their academic goals. Conversely, there is no significantly lower mean score among the statements, indicating consistent satisfaction across all aspects.

However, it is notable that the mean scores for the provision of extra materials by the teacher and the alignment of podcast content with other resources are slightly lower compared to the statement on matching learning goals. While still indicating strong agreement, this suggests areas where educators can further enhance the integration of podcasts with supplementary materials to enrich the learning experience. These findings highlight the critical role of aligning podcast content with learning objectives and integrating it seamlessly with other educational materials.

Table 10. *Summary of Students' Perception on the Utilization of Podcast Design*

Variables	Mean	SD	VI
Length	4.36	0.41	Agree
Pedagogical approach	4.44	0.42	Agree
Style	4.56	0.36	Strongly agree
Fit with other Materials	4.64	0.32	Strongly agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 (Strongly Agree) 3.50-4.49 (Agree) 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Agree) 1.50-2.49 (Disagree) 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 10 showcases students' perception regarding the utilization of podcast design, encompassing four key aspects: length, pedagogical approach, style, and fit with other materials. The highest mean score across all evaluated aspects of podcast design utilization is 4.64, indicating strong agreement among students regarding the fit of the podcast with other materials. This suggests that students highly value the integration of podcasts with other learning resources to enhance their overall learning experience. Conversely, the lowest mean score is associated with consistency in episode length, with a mean score of 4.36. This indicates slightly lower satisfaction and highlights the importance of ensuring predictability and comfort for students. Overall, these findings underscore the critical role of aligning podcast content with learning objectives and integrating it seamlessly with other educational materials.

The positive result of the podcast design aligns with Drew's (2017) research findings on several fronts. Firstly, the variation in podcast length challenges conventional wisdom, with longer podcasts—especially those engaging in storytelling or panel discussions—achieving significant online engagement and undermining the notion that podcasts should be strictly short and direct. Secondly, while many podcasts primarily focus on knowledge transmission, science-themed podcasts demonstrate more dialogic approaches through panel discourse, encouraging analytical engagement among listeners. Lastly, the informal style prevalent in podcasts, often incorporating humor and unscripted discussions, reflects a consensus in podcasting literature. Additionally, the integration of podcasts with associated websites offering supplementary materials underscores their central role in content delivery, challenging the conventional view of podcasts as merely supplemental resources within the educational landscape, as often suggested in the literature (Hew & Cheung, 2013). This comprehensive approach to podcasting not only enriches the learning experience but also highlights the potential for further exploration and innovation in educational podcast design.

Table 11 illustrates the pretest and posttest results regarding the level of agricultural literacy among participants in the utilization of podcasting as a localized supplementary learning tool in agri-crop production, specifically within the cognitive domain.

Table 11. Respondents' Pretest and Posttest on Cognitive Domain in the Utilization of Podcasting as A Localized Learning Tool in Agri-Crop Production

		Cognitive skills												
		Pretest 1		Pretest 2		Pretest 3		Posttest 1		Posttest 2		Posttest 3		VI
Scores		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
4--5	3	4.17	30	41.67	30	41.67	37	51.39	58	80.56	56	77.78	Excellent	
2--3	24	33.33	36	50	31	43.06	23	31.94	13	18.06	10	13.89	Good	
0--1	45	62.5	6	8.33	11	15.28	12	16.67	1	1.39	6	8.33	Poor	

The cognitive results from the pretest sessions indicate a notable improvement in participants' understanding of agricultural concepts over time. Initially, during Pretest 1 focused on "Use of Tools and Equipment in Farming", the majority of respondents scored in the lower ranges (0-1), reflecting a baseline level of understanding. By Pretest 2, which assessed "Preventive Maintenance of Tools and Equipment" there was a significant increase in cognitive scores, with 41.67% achieving the highest range (4-5), demonstrating improved comprehension. Pretest 3, focusing on "Interpreting Plans and Drawings" further showcased enhanced cognitive performance. The posttest results consistently showed cognitive enhancement across all sessions, with a substantial proportion of participants achieving excellent scores (4-5), particularly notable in Posttest 2 (80.56%). These findings highlight the effectiveness of podcasting as a localized learning tool in agri-crop production, fostering deep comprehension of agricultural concepts among participants.

Table 12. Respondents' Pretest and Posttest on Affective Domain in the Utilization of Podcasting as A Localized Learning Tool in Agri-Crop Production

		Affective skills												
		Pretest 1		Pretest 2		Pretest 3		Posttest 1		Posttest 2		Posttest 3		VI
Scores		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
4--5	3	4.17	10	13.89	3	4.17	26	36.11	49	72.06	30	41.67	Excellent	
2--3	40	55.56	43	59.72	42	58.33	44	61.11	13	19.12	34	47.22	Good	
0--1	29	40.28	19	26.39	27	37.5	2	2.78	6	8.82	8	11.11	Poor	

Table 12 illustrates the pretest and posttest results regarding the level of agricultural literacy among participants in the utilization of podcasting as a localized supplementary learning tool in agri-crop production, specifically within the affective domain. The affective results from the pretest and posttest sessions demonstrate consistent positive engagement among participants using podcasting as a localized learning tool in agri-crop production. Initially, during Pretest 1 focused on "Use of Tools and Equipment in Farming," a significant portion of students, 55.56% scored in the moderate range (2-3) in the affective dimension, reflecting a generally positive attitude towards the subject matter. This pattern of affective scores remained relatively stable throughout Pretest 2, which assessed "Preventive Maintenance of Tools and Equipment," with 59.72% of participants showing positive engagement, and Pretest 3, focusing on "Interpreting Plans and Drawings," where 58.33% of participants exhibited positive affective engagement. In the posttest sessions, there was further improvement in affective engagement, with scores of 2-3 reaching 61.11% and an increase in 4-5 scores to 72.06% of the students. Additionally, there was a notable increase in affective engagement in Posttest 3, where 41.67% of participants demonstrated positive attitudes and emotions towards agricultural learning. These findings suggest that while podcasting effectively enhances cognitive understanding, it also plays a crucial role in fostering positive attitudes and emotions towards agricultural learning. The consistent positive engagement in the affective dimension underscores the potential of podcasting as a valuable educational tool that not only deepens comprehension but also cultivates a more positive and engaged learning experience in agri-crop production.

Table 13. Respondents' Pretest and Posttest on Psychomotor Domain in the Utilization of Podcasting as A Localized Learning Tool in Agri-Crop Production

		Psychomotor skills												
		Pretest 1		Pretest 2		Pretest 3		Posttest 1		Posttest 2		Posttest 3		VI
Scores		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
43-50	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	28	9	13	33	46	Excellent	
35-42	1	1	6	8	0	0	43	60	42	58	31	43	Good	
27-34	20	28	35	49	61	85	9	13	19	26	8	11	Fair	
26--below	51	71	31	43	11	15	0	0	2	3	0	0	Poor	

The pretest data reveal a diverse distribution across psychomotor skill levels, with a substantial portion of respondents initially falling into the lower ranges of psychomotor ability. However, the posttest results demonstrate a notable improvement across all psychomotor

skill category, with a significant shift towards higher proficiency levels. Particularly striking is the increase in the number of participants achieving an excellent grade (43-50), rising from zero in the pretest to 46% in posttest 3. While declining from 71% in the pretest to 0% in posttest 3 of participants who got 26 and below grade. This suggests that podcasting plays a pivotal role in enhancing participants' psychomotor skills in agri-crop production, leading to more proficient and competent practitioners. Additionally, the consistent improvement observed across all skill categories underscores the broad-reaching impact of podcasting as an effective tool for skill development in agricultural contexts. These findings underscore the transformative potential of podcasting as a localized learning tool in bolstering agricultural literacy and fostering practical expertise, with implications for promoting sustainable agricultural practices and empowering individuals within the agricultural sector.

The study assessed cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains within Agri-crop Production education, with specific competencies linked to each domain. Cognitive 1, Affective 1, and Psychomotor 1 focused on "Use of Tools and Equipment in Farming," while Cognitive 2, Affective 2, and Psychomotor 2 covered "Preventive Maintenance of Tools and Equipment," and Cognitive 3, Affective 3, and Psychomotor 3 addressed "Interpreting Plans and Drawings."

Table 14. *Test of Difference between Pre-test and Post test scores of the Respondents on the Cognitive, Affective and Psychomotor Domain in Agri-crop Production*

	Pretest		Posttest		t	df	Sig (2-tailed)
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Cognitive 1	3.15	1.58	6.47	2.11	-11.345	71	0.000
Cognitive 2	5.53	2.08	8.11	2.19	-9.852	71	0.000
Cognitive 3	4.72	1.82	7.39	2.33	-9.939	71	0.000
Psychomotor 1	25.53	3.65	39.78	4.93	-25.041	71	0.000
Psychomotor 2	28.17	4.26	37.92	4.96	-19.133	71	0.000
Psychomotor 3	27.94	1.64	41.01	4.02	-28.774	71	0.000

Table 14 shows the Test of difference between Pre-test and Post test scores of the Respondents on the Cognitive, Affective and Psychomotor Domain in Agri-crop Production. It shows that there is a significant difference in the pretest and post-test results in cognitive domains 1, 2, and 3 at t values of 8.040, 7.771, and 7.768 respectively. The result also shows that there is a significant difference in the pretest and post-test results in affective domains 1, 2, and 3 at t values of 9.768, 8.301, and 7.921 respectively. The result also shows that there is a significant difference in the pretest and post-test results in psychomotor domains 1, 2, and 3 at t values of 25.041, 19.133, and 28.774 respectively.

The findings presented reveal a significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores across cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains in the context of Agri-crop Production education. In the cognitive domain, the observed t-values for domains 1, 2, and 3 respectively, with p-values below 0.05. This suggests that there was a notable improvement in cognitive understanding among respondents following the instructional intervention.

Similarly, in the affective domain, the t-values for domains 1, 2, and 3 respectively, coupled with p-values below the significance threshold, indicate a significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores. This suggests a positive shift in respondents' attitudes, values, and perceptions towards Agri-crop Production after undergoing the educational program.

Moreover, in the psychomotor domain, the substantial t-values for domains 1, 2, and 3 respectively, with p-values below 0.05, indicate a significant improvement in practical skills among respondents following the intervention. This highlights the effectiveness of the instructional approach in enhancing hands-on abilities related to Agri-crop Production.

These results have important implications for Agri-crop Production education. The significant improvements observed across cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains underscore the efficacy of the instructional program in fostering holistic learning outcomes. Educators can use these findings to justify the adoption of similar instructional strategies aimed at promoting comprehensive skill development in agricultural education.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the study reveals a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores in the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains. Since the results showed significant differences in the pretest and posttest scores, the hypothesis is not supported by difference. Thus, the hypothesis is not sustained.

Since there is a significant difference in the pretest and posttest scores in the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains, several recommendations can be made to further enhance the effectiveness of utilizing podcasting as a localized learning tool in agri-crop production:

Teachers and podcast content creators may address the need for further customization of podcast content to local agricultural situations. This could involve incorporating more specific examples and case studies relevant to the listeners' communities. Understanding the local context can greatly enhance engagement and relevance for educators and podcast producers aiming to connect effectively with their audience in agricultural contexts.

To enhance listeners' comprehension, teachers and podcast content creators may focus on improving the organization and clarity of podcast discussions. This can be achieved by structuring episodes more clearly, incorporating concise summaries or key takeaways, and utilizing visual aids or supplementary materials where applicable to reinforce learning. These strategies will contribute to better understanding and engagement with the content presented in podcasts.

Teachers and podcast content creators may consider producing shorter, more frequent episodes to better align with the target audience's preferences. This approach can help maintain listener engagement and accommodate shorter attention spans, especially among younger audiences.

Exploring ways to incorporate interactive elements into podcast episodes to foster collaborative learning experiences can greatly benefit educators and podcast content creators. This could involve incorporating quizzes, discussion prompts, or opportunities for listener participation to actively engage the audience and reinforce learning objectives. These interactive features can enhance listener involvement and make the podcast content more dynamic and memorable.

Regularly gathering feedback from listeners and evaluating the effectiveness of podcast episodes can be highly beneficial for teachers and podcast content creators. This feedback loop involving the audience can be instrumental in continuously refining and optimizing future episodes, ensuring they are tailored to meet the evolving needs and preferences of the listeners.

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